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Laboratory and field evaluation of the molluscicidal effects of basil oil and basil extract against the land snail *Monacha cartusiana* (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae)

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Abstract

Terrestrial gastropods, including land snails, cause serious damage to field crops, vegetables, and orchards, as well as ornamental plants. Chemical molluscicides have a toxic impact on the environment and non-target animals; thus, plant-based molluscicides provide a convenient alternative. In this study, the molluscicidal activity of basil oil and basil extract against the land snail *Monacha cartusiana* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) was evaluated. Several concentrations of basil oil and basil extract were used as poison bait to evaluate mortality rates and the LC₅₀. Moreover, sub-lethal concentration (LC₂₅) was used to detect biochemical and histological investigation. The population reduction percent was evaluated under field conditions. The toxicity test showed that the LC₅₀ was 3.56 and 3.40 g/L for oil and extract. Treatment with basil oil and basil extract enhanced disturbance in antioxidant/oxidant biomarkers, decreasing GSH content and GST activity, as well as increasing MDA activity. Furthermore, total lipid, total protein, and acetylcholine esterase levels declined in treated snails. Meanwhile, treatments promoted pathological alterations in the foot and digestive gland. Additionally, a significant reduction in the *M. cartusiana* population after treatment application in the clover field was observed. Finally, basil oil and basil extract can be used as safe alternative molluscicides for land snail control programs.

Introduction

Land snails are crucial pests that pose a threat to sustainable agriculture, playing a critical role in transmitting and spreading diseases to plants (Gazzy *et al.*, 2019; Kandil *et al.*, 2020; and Bashandy *et al.*, 2023). Recently, phytochemical screening has revealed that numerous plants possess pesticidal properties, which can be utilized economically for pest control (Sola *et*

al., 2014). Additionally, plant extracts have been investigated as alternatives to chemical molluscicides (Abd El-Atti *et al.*, 2019, and Ismail, 2024). Wherever the use of chemical molluscicides is expensive, environmentally unfriendly, toxic to non-target organisms, and poses challenges to sustainable agriculture (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2022, and Guo *et al.*, 2023). In this context, *Ocimum basilicum*, commonly known

as basil, is recognized as a diverse and rich source of essential oils and a significant culinary herb worldwide (Chenni *et al.*, 2016, and Nadeem *et al.*, 2020). Basil extracts are known for their potential insecticidal activity, but their molluscicidal effects on snails are less established than those of other plant-based molluscicides. More research is needed to fully understand their potential in controlling snails (Dris *et al.*, 2017; Mossalem *et al.*, 2021; and Botelho *et al.*, 2022).

Thus, in the present study, the control efficacy of methanol extract of basil (*O. basilicum*) against the clover snail *Monacha cartusiana* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) was evaluated and compared with that of its essential oil under laboratory and field conditions.

Materials and methods

1. Experimental animals:

M. cartusiana snails were collected from clover fields in Sids village, Beni-Suef Governorate, Egypt. After that, snails were transferred to the laboratory in Sids Agricultural Research Station under conditions of $20 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 weeks for acclimatization.

2. Basil leaves extraction:

Basil (*O. basilicum*) leaves were obtained from Shandaweel Agricultural Research Station, Sohag, Egypt. The elected leaves were healthy and did not show any morphological aberrations. Firstly, plant leaves were washed using tap water to remove any contaminants, and then were left to shade-dry for 2 weeks at room temperature. After that, the dried leaves were ground into a fine powder. Fifty grams of the powder were put in 500 mL of 80% methanol and then shaken for 48 h at room temperature. The produced extract was filtered through Whatman filter paper. The extracts were concentrated using a rotary evaporator at 40°C to remove any remaining methanol and then stored in a refrigerator at 4°C .

3. Basil oil:

Basil oil was obtained from El Hawag for Natural Oils, Nasr City, Cairo, Egypt.

4. Toxicity test:

Several concentrations of basil oil (0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4 g/L) and basil extract (0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6 g/L) were assessed against *M. cartusiana*, introduced as poison baits and prepared by combining each concentration with 5% molasses + 93% bran. Every five grams of the poison bait was introduced to each replicate. Ten animals were included in each replicate. Three replicates were used for each concentration. The other thirty individuals (three replicates of ten snails each) served as the control group. Mortality percent and the LC_{50} values were calculated after 1 week according to Finney (1971). Where dead snails were counted, and also, lethal concentrations (LC_{50} and LC_{90}) were computed by Probit analysis using statistical software of social sciences (SPSS) (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA).

5. Biochemical and histological investigation:

Three groups of snails (20 snails each) were used to evaluate the biochemical and histological changes. The first group was considered the control; the second group was offered LC_{25} basil oil, and the third group was offered LC_{25} basil extract for one week. Snails were dissected, and soft parts were taken for the following biochemical and histological studies. One gram of snail soft tissues was homogenized for three minutes with 10 mL of sodium chloride 0.9 N, and centrifuged (5000 rpm for 30 min). The supernatant was used to determine the biochemical markers. Glutathione content (GSH), glutathione-S-transferase (GST), and malondialdehyde activity (MDA) were evaluated using the colorimetric method (Beutler *et al.*, 1963; Habig *et*

al., 1974; and Ohkawa *et al.*, 1979). Total lipid and total protein contents were estimated according to Zöllner and Kirsch (1962) and Kinsley and Frankel (1939), respectively, using Biodiagnostic Company (Egypt) kits. Meanwhile, Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity was assayed using the Kovarik *et al.* (2003) method. The histopathological impact of basil oil and basil extract on the foot and digestive gland of *M. cartusiana* was screened. After the snails were anesthetized, the foot and the digestive gland of treated and untreated snails were taken and fixed in Bouin's solution for 24 hrs. Washing with tap water, dehydration using alcohol, clearing in xylene, and embedding in paraffin were done. Paraffin tissue blocks were cut into sections using a microtome. Sections were put on glass slides, deparaffinized, and then stained with hematoxylin and eosin stain (H and E). Prepared slides were examined using light microscopy for any histological changes in parallel with control slides (Mohamed and Saad, 1990).

6. Field experiment:

Nine plots (30 m² each) cultivated with clover and infested with *M. cartusiana* were selected at Quftan village, Beni Suef Governorate, Egypt, for field application. Three plots are left for control, and the other 6 plots for treatments (3 plots for each treatment). The most laboratory-effectively tested

concentrations of basil oil (4 g/L) and basil extract (6 g/L) were evaluated using the bait method, leaving a distance of 10 meters between the tested plots. Survivors of snails were counted in every plot pre- and post- application at 1, 3, 7, 15, and 21 days. Population reduction of snails was calculated 21 days after treatment using the equation of Henderson and Tilton (1952).

7. Statistical analysis:

By using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) (SPSS, version 20), a statistical program (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA), data was analyzed. Analysis of differences between the means of different groups was performed using Duncan's multiple range test and a two-tailed paired t-test. Lethal concentration values and their respective 95% confidence limit (CL) were calculated by Probit analysis (Finney, 1971).

Results and discussion

1. Toxicity tests:

The results elucidate that the impact of basil oil and basil extract on the *M. cartusiana* snail was concentration dependent. Meanwhile, it was observed that as their concentration increased, the mortality rate of *M. cartusiana* snails significantly decreased. The highest mortality percentages (60 and 80%) were reached at the tested concentrations of (4 and 6 g/L), and the LC₅₀ was achieved at concentrations of (3.56 and 3.40 g/L), and the LC₉₀ was (6.92 and 6.38 g/L) for basil oil and basil extract, respectively (Table 1).

Table (1): Molluscicidal activity of basil oil and basil extract against *Monacha cartusiana* snails.

Treatment	Conc.g/l	Mortality % Mean ± SEM	LC ₅₀ (95% CL)	LC ₉₀ (95% CL)
Basil oil	0.5	10.00 ± 1.58 ^b	3.56	6.92
	1	20.00 ± 2.74 ^c		
	2	30.00 ± 2.74 ^d		
	3	35.00 ± 2.24 ^e		
	4	60.00 ± 2.23 ^f		
Basil extract	0.5	5.00 ± 1.58 ^a	3.40	6.38
	1	15.00 ± 2.24 ^b		
	2	30.00 ± 1.58 ^c		
	3	45.00 ± 4.1 ^d		
	4	70.00 ± 1.58 ^e		
	6	80.00 ± 2.74 ^f		
Control		0.00 ± 0.00 ^a		

Data are represented as a mean ± SEM. Different symbols in the same line, significant difference in comparison with the corresponding control at $\alpha=0.05$ (P<0.05).

2. Biochemical investigations:

The treatment of *M. cartusiana* with a sublethal dose (LC₂₅) of basil oil and basil extract imbalanced the oxidant/antioxidant status and significantly decreased both GSH content ($P \leq 0.001$) and GST activity ($P \leq 0.05$, $P \leq 0.01$), respectively. Moreover, treatments significantly increased MDA level ($P \leq 0.01$, $P \leq$

0.001) for basil oil and basil extract (Figures 1 and 2). Total lipids and total protein significantly declined ($P \leq 0.001$) after exposure to the LC₂₅ of both treatments (Figures 3 and 4). Meanwhile, acetylcholinesterase activity significantly reduced ($P \leq 0.05$, $P \leq 0.001$) for basil oil and basil extract, respectively (Figure 5).

Figure (1): Effect of treatments of LC₂₅ of basil oil and basil extract on GSH content and MDA activity in *Monacha cartusiana* along with their respective controls. *, *** Significantly different at $P < 0.05$, $P < 0.001$ over their respective controls.

Figure (2): Effect of treatments of LC₂₅ of basil oil and basil extract on GST activity in *Monacha cartusiana* along with their respective controls. *, ** Significantly different at $P < 0.05$, $P < 0.01$ over their respective controls.

Figure (3): Effect of treatments of LC₂₅ of basil oil and basil extract on total lipid content in *Monacha cartusiana*, along with their respective controls. *** Significantly different at P <0.001 over their respective controls.

Figure (4): Effect of treatments of LC₂₅ of basil oil and basil extract on total protein content in *Monacha cartusiana*, along with their respective controls. *** Significantly different at P <0.001 over their respective controls.

Figure (5): Effect of treatments of LC₂₅ of basil oil and basil extract on total lipid content in *Monacha cartusiana* along with their respective controls. *, *** Significantly different at P<0.05, P <0.001 over their respective controls.

3. Histological studies:

Basil oil and basil extract showed noticeable effects on the foot and digestive gland. Treatment with basil oil and basil extract induced destruction of epithelium cells, deformation of muscle fibers, and hyperplasia of

pigment cells compared with the normal structure in controls (Figure 6). Basil oil treatment produced degeneration and rupture, of digestive cells. Basil extract enhances cellular blebs, rupture, and degeneration of digestive cells (Figure 7).

Figure (6): Light micrographs showing the effect of basil oil and basil extract on the foot of *Monacha cartusiana* snails. (a) Normal foot, EC, epithelium cell, MG: mucus gland, MF: Mussel fiber, pigment cell (PC). (b) Treated snails with basil oil showing destruction of epithelium cells (DEC), deformed muscle fibers (DMF), and hyperplasia of pigment cells (PC). (c) Treated snails with basil extract showing destruction of epithelium cells (DEC), hyperplasia of pigment cell (PC), and deformed muscle fiber (DMF). (X 200).

Figure (7): Light micrographs showing the effect of basil oil and basil extract on the digestive gland of *Monacha cartusiana*, snails (a) Control, digestive tubule (DT), digestive cell (DC), excretory cell (EC), lumen (L). (b) Basil oil-treated snails showing the presence of degeneration of digestive cells (DDC), rupture (RDC) of digestive cells. (c) Basil extract-treated snails showing the presence of cellular blebs, rupture (RDC), and degeneration (DDC) of digestive cells. (X 200).

4. Field efficacy

The field performance of basil oil and basil extract against the *M. cartusiana* population is shown in Table (2). Basil oil and basil extract

significantly decreased the snail population by 79.35% and 82.15%, respectively, as compared with the untreated control group (Table 2).

Table (2): Field performance of basil oil and basil extract against land snails, *Monacha cartusiana*, compared with control after 21 days of treatment.

Treatment	No. pretreatment	No. post treatment	t	P	Percent of change
Basil oil	37.4± 1.21	8.40± 0.51	24.51	0.001	79.35
Basil extract	34.00±1.92	6.60±0.51	11.95	0.001	82.15
Control	38.8 ± 1.66	42.20± 1.80	1.22	0.289	

Our study showed the toxic impact of basil oil and basil extract on snail individuals, resulting in their mortality. These results are in line with Bashandy and Awwad (2024). Basel's toxic action

may return to active constituents like eugenol, methyl eugenol, linalool, methyl chavicol, estragole, citral, and (E)-methyl cinnamate (Bhavva *et al.*, 2018, and Costa *et al.*, 2020). Stress

perturbs the internal balance of organisms (homeostasis) and affects the structure, function, growth, stability, and survival of cells, provoking reactive oxygen species responses at the cellular level and motivating antioxidant mechanisms (Chandrasekaran *et al.*, 2017). Immoderate stress can motivate this response into a death signal (Lloyd-Price *et al.*, 2019). Sub-lethal dose exposure to snails caused an imbalance of the oxidant/antioxidant markers *via* increasing the activity of the lipid peroxidation enzyme MDA, and declining the antioxidants, GSH content, and GST activity in the present study. Cell responses to stress affect various critical functions: cell cycle regulation, protein repair, damaged protein removal, and metabolism (Laberge *et al.*, 2012, and Dos Santos *et al.*, 2018).

The decrease in total lipids and total protein content in our study may be related to basil, which can affect mitochondria, which are responsible for the generation of 90% of cellular energy as ATP and also regulate calcium metabolism and thermogenesis, producing high levels of ROS, causing oxidative destruction in proteins, lipids, and DNA (Dasha *et al.*, 2025). In addition to that, this depletion may be returned to a decrease in lipid synthesis capability or hydrolysis of hepatic fats as a result of stress circumstances (Gaber *et al.*, 2007, and Sayed and El-Sayed, 2020). Additionally, a reduction in protein levels in snails was supposed to be achieved by carbohydrate breakdown, which makes changes in protein production and also metabolism (Khalil, 2016). Treatments with basil oil and basil extract promoted a significant decline in the AchE activity. It was demonstrated that essential oil prepared from the basil plant exhibited significant anti-acetylcholinesterase activity (Farag *et al.*, 2016, and Mahendran and Vimolmangkang,

2023). AChE is implicated in nerve impulse transmission mechanisms throughout the body. Inhibition of this enzyme with various neurotoxic chemicals results in chemical messenger acetylcholine buildup in the synaptic region, causing continuous nerve impulse transmission and death (Cassaneli *et al.*, 2006). Moreover, histological studies in our study supported the impact of the tested compounds by induction of severe changes in the normal structure of the foot and digestive gland of snails. In addition to that, basil oil and basil extract significantly reduced the snail population under field conditions. This may return to the presence of active ingredients that have a toxic impact on snails. The present results show the potential efficiency of basil oil and basil extract as safe molluscicidal products and they could be used in the integrated pest management strategies.

Basil oil and basil extract exhibited molluscicidal effects on *M. cartusiana*. In addition, oil and extract disturb enzyme activities, affecting MDA, GST, and AchE levels. Moreover, treatment decreased the content of GSH, total lipids, and total protein and also caused histological changes in the foot and digestive gland of snails. Furthermore, treatments reduced the snail population in the field application.

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